

Some new organotellurium(II) molecular adducts with monodentate ligands

Shekhar Srivastava^{a*}, Abul Kalam^a, Hari Shankar Gupta^b and Deepa Gautam^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, University of Allahabad, Allahabad-211 002, India

^bSchool of Studies in Chemistry, Jiwaji University, Gwalior-474 011, India

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Some molecular adducts with monodentate ligands of $(C_6H_5)_2Te$ and $(p-MeOC_6H_4)_2Te$ have synthesised. They are characterized by IR and X-ray photoelectron spectra and conductance studies.

Organotellurium compounds have attracted considerable current interest in various fields¹. The synthesis and utility of organotellurium(II) molecular adducts with various monodentate ligands are less studied^{2,3}. Here we report the synthesis of molecular adducts with various monodentate ligands of $(C_6H_5)_2Te$ and $(p-MeOC_6H_4)_2Te$.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes (Table 1) were found air-stable. Molar conductances of all the complexes ($20-30 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) indicate their nonelectrolytic nature⁴.

IR frequencies associated with the Te-C bond⁵ were identified in all the adducts at $220-260 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. In case of adducts with nitrogen donor, the $\nu_{C=N}$ modes underwent shift to higher wavenumbers suggesting the presence of coordinated base. 4-pic band (1569 cm^{-1}) shifted to 1640 cm^{-1} due to complexation⁶. In the spectra of *N*-oxides, the strong intensity band was observed at $1265 \pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (N-O). It underwent a negative shift ($\sim 20 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) on complexation, which is attributed to coordination from the oxygen atom of the Lewis base to metal atom. Absorption associated with C-H out-of-plane deformation modes underwent slight positive shift due to tightening of the aromatic ring on complexation. A positive shift of about 20 cm^{-1} was observed for these modes of vibrations⁷.

The significant negative shift of $\nu_{C=O}$ ligand vibration from $1665 \pm 15 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ to $1635 \pm 15 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ upon complexation indicates coordination via oxygen atom of the amide. This is corroborated by the positive shift of the absorption due to δ_{C-N} (contiguous to C=O) and δ_{N-C} (to CH_3) upon complexation. It has been postulated that coordination via oxygen is more favoured due to steric hindrance at the substituted nitrogen atom⁸.

The $\nu_{S=O}$ frequency of pure DMSO at 1045 cm^{-1}

shifted to 948 cm^{-1} in $R_2Te \cdot DMSO$ due to the coordination of the oxygen atom of DMSO to the Te metal. The asym and sym stretching of C-S modes of the free ligands were identified at 705 and 665 cm^{-1} , respectively⁹. Due to weak intensity of these absorptions and their close proximity to the strong C-H out-of-plane deformation modes, it has not been possible to identify them in the spectra of the adduct with certainty, but a slight positive shift is generally indicated. The ν_{P-O} vibration in the free base triphenylphosphine oxide around 1192 cm^{-1} shifted to lower frequency by $\sim 20 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in molecular adducts¹⁰, showing coordination of triphenylphosphine oxide to the Te metal ion through oxygen atom.

The binding energies of R_2Te and their adducts $R_2Te \cdot L$ for $Te 3d_{3/2,5/2}$ photoelectron peaks and the value of NIs and OIs binding energies are listed in Table 1. The binding energy of $Te 3d_{3/2,5/2}$ in starting material R_2Te was found higher than their molecular adducts $R_2Te \cdot L$. This indicates that the electron density on the metal ion is increased by coordination¹¹. Moreover, the $P 2p$ binding energies in the triphenylphosphine has been increased in $R_2Te \cdot PPh_3$, suggesting increase of positive charge on the P atom. This concludes the coordination of P of PPh_3 with Te metal ion of R_2Te ¹¹, forming molecular adduct $R_2Te \cdot PPh_3$. The $Te 3s$ photoelectron peak of all the molecular adducts of the type $R_2Te \cdot L$ has shown single symmetrical peak without any splitting in photoelectron peak. The observed $Te 3s$ photoelectron peaks confirm the diamagnetic nature of these molecular adducts¹¹.

Hence, it may be concluded that all the adducts possess trigonal bipyramidal (sp^3d hybridisation) structure due to the presence of two lone-pairs on the Te atom as shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Geometry of $R_2Te.L$.Table 1. $Te3d_{3/2}$, $5p_2$, NIs and OIs binding energies (eV) of R_2Te and their $R_2Te.L$ adducts (L = monodentate ligands)^a

Compd.	Te		NIs	OIs
	$Te3d_{3/2}$	$Te3d_{5/2}$		
$(C_6H_5)_2Te$	586.0	575.8	-	-
$(C_6H_5)_2Te$.pyridine	585.2	574.0	402.8	-
$(C_6H_5)_2Te$.pyridine- <i>N</i> -oxide	585.0	574.0	402.6	532.8
$(C_6H_5)_2Te$.morpholine	585.2	574.0	-	-
$(C_6H_5)_2Te$.4-picoline	585.0	574.0	402.6	-
$(C_6H_5)_2Te$. $N(CH_3)_3$	585.1	574.2	402.8	-
$(C_6H_5)_2Te$.DMSO	585.0	574.0	-	532.8
$(C_6H_5)_2Te$.DMF	585.2	574.2	-	532.6
$(C_6H_5)_2Te$.triphenylphosphine sulfide	585.0	574.0	-	-
$(C_6H_5)_2Te$.triphenylphosphine oxide	585.0	574.0	-	532.8
$(C_6H_5)_2Te$.PPh ₃	585.0	574.0	-	-
$(p-MeOC_6H_4)_2Te$	585.4	575.2	-	-
$(p-MeOC_6H_4)_2Te$.pyridine	585.0	575.0	403.4	-
$(p-MeOC_6H_4)_2Te$.pyridine- <i>N</i> -oxide	583.8	574.2	403.2	-
$(p-MeOC_6H_4)_2Te$.morpholine	583.6	574.0	-	-
$(p-MeOC_6H_4)_2Te$.4-picoline	583.6	574.2	403.4	-
$(p-MeOC_6H_4)_2Te$. $N(CH_3)_3$	583.4	574.2	403.2	-
$(p-MeOC_6H_4)_2Te$.DMSO	583.6	574.2	-	-
$(p-MeOC_6H_4)_2Te$.DMF	583.6	574.0	-	-
$(p-MeOC_6H_4)_2Te$.triphenylphosphine sulfide	583.4	574.0	-	-
$(p-MeOC_6H_4)_2Te$.triphenylphosphine oxide	583.4	574.0	-	-
$(p-MeOC_6H_4)_2Te$.PPh ₃	583.6	574.0	-	-

^aAll compounds gave satisfactory Te, C, H and N analyses

Experimental

The $(C_6H_5)_2Te^{12}$ and $(p-MeOC_6H_4)_2Te^{13}$ were prepared by literature procedures.

$(C_6H_5)_2Te$ or $(p-MeOC_6H_4)_2Te$ (1 mmol) in dry chloroform (25 ml) was refluxed with pyridine or pyridine-*N*-oxide/morpholine/4-picoline/trimethylamine/dimethyl sulfoxide/dimethylformamide/triphenylphosphine sulfide/triphenylphosphine oxide/triphenylphosphine (1 mmol) for 3 h then rotary-evaporated and left overnight in the deep freeze. The crystals obtained were washed with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) and dried under reduced pressure.

Conductance was measured in acetone at room temperature using a Digisun conductivity bridge. Infrared spectra (CsI) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 457 spectrophotometer. X-Ray photoelectron spectra were recorded on a VG Scientific ESCA-3MK II electron spectrometer¹¹ in triplicate. In most of the cases the binding energies were reproducible within ± 0.1 eV.

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